

Report by **Bryan S. Buckner**

Analyzing The Importance of Various Human Resource Functions

Analyzing the Importance of Various Human Resource Functions

Introduction

Human resources function is to work transferring all employees or collaborators of an organization . Usually the HR function consists of areas such as recruitment and selection, hiring, training, administration and personnel management while within the enterprise. Depending on the company where HR function operates, there may be other groups who hold different responsibilities that may be related to aspects such as the administration of employee payroll or management of relations with unions, among others . To implement the strategy of the organization is critical management of human resources, for which it must consider concepts such as organizational communication , the leadership , the teamwork , the negotiation and organizational culture (Price, A. 2011).

Recruitment and Employee Selection

Recruitment is the process of attracting candidates for a vacancy, advertising and making attractive to candidates on the market while organizational objectives can be achieved only with and through people. The main objective of selection is to hire the best of the candidates, a process by which one makes the choice of candidates with the required profile for the position. HR ensures high potential people for entry and quality in the organization, which is the goal of any business because the human side of the company must provide consistency in terms of policies and recruitment and selection practices (Ulrich, D. 2013). The alignment of human resources with the company's strategy is very important as strategic planning is a powerful tool for building and consolidating its image. Only with planning is possible to establish an integrated

communication that gives consistency and leverage the message at all points of contact with the market, it is one of the most important elements for a successful human resources management program, is a process by which the organization ensures the right number and the right people in the right place (Mathis, R. L., & Jackson, J. 2011).

The choice of people is held satisfaction, the best and most efficient way possible, in order to benefit the company, the company already has a good chance of success, based on the people who compose it. Therefore, the selection process deserves special attention, since it is he who will define in different ways and with different strategies, which candidate will get the job. And every selection process should have a strategic plan, with long-term goals, so that any occurrences will not harm the smooth running of the company, especially if the replacements are not selected efficiently(Ulrich, D. 2013).

Recruitment may be internal or external; the recruitment is internal when an organization chooses the appropriate employee within the organization for the specific vacancy, the company seeks to fill it through relocation of their employees, which can be promoted, transferred within the company departments or branches (Price, A. 2011). While the recruitment abroad is a way to attract new candidates from outside the organization and look fill vacancies with foreign applicants to the company and that are able to meet the need of selection, which is to select the best prepared candidate to fill the vacancy.

Utilization of human capital resources

The management of human resources has changed, we've all witnessed, at least in part, to change the names and personnel management practices, and, successively, the management of

human resources, people, human capital. There several ways in the management of people in organizations (Mathis, R. L., & Jackson, J. 2011).

The first way in HR management was the coordination of policies and HR practices with each other. From this point of view, people are an asset that can be managed systematically and co-ordinately (Mathis, R. L., & Jackson, J. 2011). HRM internal consistency is sought in a way that can be called integrated. Although not widespread way some HR managers already know that integrated people management practices influence behavior and can produce positive results (Ulrich, D. 2013).

The second way is the recognition of the need to coordinate the HRM with the needs and goals of the organization. This is clearly the broad strategic perspective of HR which seeks the effectiveness of policies and practices adopted to find the right number of people with the necessary skills, abilities, experience and the appropriate knowledge and motivation levels adjusted to the organization (Mathis, R. L., & Jackson, J. 2011). This is what recently began to be called human capital. The strategic management of HR is well condition to achieve fundamental goals ranging from customer satisfaction and employees to profitability and survival of the organization (Mathis, R. L., & Jackson, J. 2011).

Balancing Organization Needs with Employees

Modern organizations in the market have come to the conclusion that investing in their employees is the most effective way and the shortest and safest way to achieve their goals (Ulrich, D. 2013). If an organization depends directly on the behavior of people who provide services to it is imperative that keep these people trained, well prepared and highly motivated mainly for the tasks they will perform (Price, A. 2011).

Need to assess the real needs of the organization and the employee so that organization can establish the desired level of performance. In addition, it is necessary that the company is willing to make room and provide opportunities for people to apply new skills (Ulrich, D. 2013). The development process of the people means not only provides knowledge and skills so they can do their jobs more productively. It also means providing them with training to enable them to develop new attitudes and empower to increase their knowledge in pursuit of becoming better at what they do (Price, A. 2011). Therefore, it is to go beyond a personal training, involving aspects that approach the education process. With this, some companies have preferred to treat the issue referring to this as education for work, and the training of professionals known as educators. People are not part of the productive life of organizations (Ulrich, D. 2013). They are the essential principle of dynamics, they give vitality to the activities and processes, innovate, create, recreate contexts and situations that can lead the organization to position themselves competitively, cooperative and differentiated with customers, other organizations and the business environment in general. Importantly invest in the development of the people of the organization is to invest in the quality of products and services, better serve customers and increase revenues (Mathis, R. L., & Jackson, J. 2011).

Providing security and comfort for employees, schedule flexibility and predictability initiatives and deadlines, providing learning opportunities especially to the younger ones, recognizing employees by giving promotion opportunities are the few examples to balancing the organization needs together with the employees (Mathis, R. L., & Jackson, J. 2011).

Organizational Leadership and HR

Leadership can be exercised in various ways and on many levels. Will always depend on who is the leader and who the led for what. To be successful, especially in the workplace, you must choose the right style for the right group, always remembering that today man is much more focused on the relationship than for the task (Price, A. 2011). The leader who realize this will much more easily to exercise their leadership, success and satisfaction, strategically, assertive and collaborator (Price, A. 2011).

The company is an organization composed of people who behave in many different ways. Can be stressed, calm, nervous, and sad, quiet, restless, among other endless quotes, and is primarily for these reasons that companies should use the emotional intelligence tool to your advantage (Price, A. 2011). In addition to performing the tasks incumbent upon their duties, people need to live in harmony to produce and are not easy to live a harmony when it spends much of her time within the work environment, dealing with people so different (Ulrich, D. 2013).

Conclusion

The right human resources management is essential for companies to successfully meet their cost targets, talent management, and process efficiency. Generally, the policy of human resources focuses on ensuring that employees are on the same page that the company, matching the yearnings and aspirations of workers with the strategy of the company. The assembly of an efficient workforce, building a good working environment and development potential of each employee are some common objectives in the field of human resources. The purpose of human resources managers of a company is that workers are satisfied with their jobs and, therefore,

strive to meet the goals of the organization. Training, promotion and merit pay scale for a just retribution are some of the variables that usually employ in their work. Likewise, we must also emphasize that HR managers to encourage enthusiasm and desire of employees in the performance of their duties often resort to what is known as incentive. Among them would be found from a percentage of the profits achieved so bonds of various kinds.

References

Mathis, R. L., & Jackson, J. (2011). Human resource management: Essential perspectives.

Cengage Learning.

Price, A. (2011). Human resource management. Cengage Learning.

Ulrich, D. (2013). Human resource champions: The next agenda for adding value and delivering results. Harvard Business Press.